

Cruise report 64PE420

***ATLAS cold-water coral
carbon cycling***

Texel - Galway

April 24th – May 12th 2017

Rockall Bank

Chief scientist: G.J. Reichart

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1. Introduction

1.1 Aim and background

Cruise 64PE420 is a NIOZ contribution to the NWO-funded VIDI project 'Surviving in a Deep-Sea Desert – Uncovering the Functioning of Cold-Water Coral Reefs in the Deep Ocean' awarded to Dick van Oevelen (grant number 864.13.007) and the EU-funded ATLAS program (www.eu-atlas.org) funded to Dick van Oevelen and Gerard Duineveld.

The deep seafloor harbors one of the most biodiverse ecosystems on our planet: cold-water coral reefs. Like their tropical counterparts, cold-water corals (CWCs) form structurally complex habitats that support a diverse and productive reef community. It is still paradoxical how such a rich ecosystem can thrive in the deep sea; an environment that is typically considered to be food limited. The VIDI and ATLAS project collectively target this paradox by an integrated study on the delivery, uptake and processing of organic matter by cold-water coral reef communities along Rockall Bank (West of Ireland, Fig. 1), an area that has amongst the highest abundance of cold-water coral reefs in the world.

The basis of this study is a framework for the functioning of CWC-reef communities in the deep sea, which is based on hypotheses generated from preliminary findings, and has three key elements: (1) direct field measurements indicate that organic matter respiration by CWC-reef communities is much higher than respiration in off-reef sediments, indicating an enhanced organic matter uptake, (2) a coupled hydrodynamic-biogeochemical model suggests that this enhanced uptake can be explained by episodic vertical transport of organic matter, focused to the reef community and (3) recycling of organic matter within the reef community, with sponges as key mediator, ensures the retention and efficient utilization of available organic matter.

This conceptual framework will be verified and validated for the 600-m deep CWC reefs at Rockall Bank (Irish Margin) through the integration of empirical data, acquired with state-of-the-art measurement techniques, and mathematical models. Models will guide sampling strategies, while the data will feed back into the models for calibration and fine-tuning. The validated models will lead to an improved understanding of the functioning of this unique ecosystem in the present-day and will allow forecasting future effects of reduced organic matter export to the deep sea on the functioning CWC-reef communities. One of the measurement techniques will be further developed with industry partners for use in environmental impact studies.

The output of this study area will be used to improve our current capacity to predict CWC distribution and functioning along continental shelves, which present relies on statistical models with physical predictors (e.g. temperature, salinity and aragonite saturation state). The high OM processing power of CWCs means that these animals overcome the food limited conditions of the deep seafloor, yet organic matter availability has to date not been used as a biological predictor. Accurate predictions can only be made if physical transport mechanisms such as downslope transport of surface waters, downward convection over reefs or vertical eddy flux are measured together with OM delivery.

Specific goals of this cruise

The specific goals of this cruise are therefore:

- 1) To better quantify carbon and nutrient cycling of CWC-reef communities. This end, we will deploy the ALBEX lander that is equipped with a profile pump to collect water samples in a

gradient above the reef framework. The water samples will be analyzed for nutrients, bacteria and dissolved organic matter. The ALBEX lander will also be equipped with an Aquatic Eddy Covariance (AEC) system to determine the oxygen uptake rate of the reef framework. Large boxcores (50 cm i.d.) will be taken from the reef framework and incubated onboard for oxygen uptake and nutrient release in temperature-controlled basins. Reef organisms will be sampled using the ROV *Genesis* and incubated separately onboard. The ROV will also be used to insert an oxygen sensor in the reef framework to investigate the oxygenation within the reef framework.

- 2) To better understand the transport of organic matter towards the CWC-reefs, a series of benthic-pelagic coupling measurements will be done. A thermistor string will be deployed above Haas mound to investigate downward mixing of surface water. Two long-term moorings will be deployed on Oreo Mound (650 m deep) and higher-up Rockall Bank (400 m) that are equipped with upward looking ADCPs, a sediment trap and one (Bank station) or two (Oreo Mound) FLNTU to measure fluorescence and optical backscatter in the water column. At both long-term mooring sites, 24 hour CTDs station will be done. In situ pumps (at three depths) will be deployed to and zooplankton will be used to sample the organic matter in the water column.

1.2 Scientific crew

Gert-Jan Reichart, NIOZ/UU	Chief scientist
Dick van Oevelen, NIOZ	ROV transects
Furu Mienis, NIOZ	ALBEX lander/CTD
Gerard Duineveld, NIOZ	Long-term moorings/in situ O2 sensor
Marc Lavaleye, NIOZ	Zooplankton tows/boxcore incubations
Sandra Maier, NIOZ	Fauna incubations
Evert de Froe, NIOZ	Boxcore incubations
Lorenzo Rovelli, SDU	Aquatic eddy covariance
Sabena Blackbird, UL	In situ pumps
Wim Versteeg, VLIZ	ROV operation
Michiel T'Jampens, VLIZ	ROV operation

2. ATLAS cruise

Transit

We left the harbor of Texel, with one day delay, on April 25th (16.00 local time) for a ± 4 -day transit to the first station at Rockall Bank. Transit south of UK and Ireland was smooth, but West of Ireland a reasonable swell was encountered. The clock on the ship was set (1 hour in the night of 26th April and 1 hour 28th of April) to UTC to correspond to local time and to time on scientific equipment. We reached the first station, top of Haas Mound, on April 29th around 17.00u (UTC).

April 29th

Station 1

Arrival on first station around 17.00UTC

Deployment of thermistor string. Station coordinates of deployment: 55°29.87N / 15°46.99W.

The location of the thermistor has been determined by triangulation, using three locations.

Station 2

CTD for OBS calibration. CTD kept at constant depths (4) for ±10 minutes for calibration of all OBS systems (1 to be used on the CTD, 3 that will go on the LT-moorings). 2 Niskin bottles closed at each depth for PO, SPM, DOC, DIC and NUTS (see Appendix). Another 10 Niskin bottles closed for incubation water (deepest point) and sensor calibration water for AEC. OBS calibration was successful, but the shallow water OBS (VLIZ) gave (much) lower readings compared to the deep-water ones. This might be due to a different preset measuring window?

Transit to in situ pump station on top of Haas mound.

Station 3

In situ pumps deployed at 520m (20 mab), 75m (465 mab) and 15m (525 mab). Runtime between 23:00 and 02:00 UTC. SAPS left in the water until 07:00 on the CTD. All Niskin bottles closed directly after reaching deepest point to be used as incubation water upon retrieval.

April 30th

Station 3, continued

Recovery of in situ pumps and CTD. CTD was between 12 and 30 mab during whole deployment, with sensors that were continuously logging. CTD on deck at 07.30UTC. Water collected for incubation water and filters recovered by Sabena.

Station 4

Deployment of boxcore at 8.30. Video guidance not working, but video recorded on the boxcore. On deck at 9.00UTC. Boxcore failed, did not trip.

Station 5

Boxcore was closed upon recovery and was sampled on deck for water column. The box water was somewhat murky, but placed in incubation bath and to be inspected later when the water has cleared.

Station 6

Boxcore successfully closed. Living coral visible. Placed in water bath. Temperature 8.5C

Station 7

Deployment of ALBEX lander. Position determined using USBL

ROV dive is cancelled, because of heavy weather

Station 8

Boxcoreing today to collect organisms for Sandra her experimental work. Moved to station along the slope (15°47.63W / 55°29.45N, 647 m). Boxcore failed, did not trip.

Station 9

Full boxcore. Sub-samples used for incubation experiments (without label) by Sandra Maier.

Station 10

Zooplankton tow to 100 m. 200 um net. Sieved on 180-um sieve. No need to separate in size classes, mostly small organisms. Not much material, mostly copepods and some swimming polychaetes.

Station 11

Zooplankton tow to 100 m. Quite full as shown below (St10 left, St11 right). A lot of copepods and swimming polychaetes, dominated by Trophophora (larvae of invertebrates).

Station 12

Zooplankton idem. Small copepods, planktonic foraminifera.

Station 13

In situ pumps deployment + incubation water. In situ pumps timed to make sure that it ran during same tidal currents as during 64PE420_3. In situ pumps successfully recovered at 22.00. All Niskin bottles were closed for incubation water.

Station 13 and 14

Planned fishfinder transects:

Transect 1: 55°29.891 / 15°52.247 to 55°29.140 / 15°43.623

Transect 2: 55°31.492 / 15°45.256 to 55°26.363 / 15°53.750

Speed 3 knots

Problem with logging encountered with the EK500 around 23.00. Decided to stop the transect and move to one position (on the flank of Haas mound). DvO will check the EK500 at 0.15 again and give it a restart if necessary. However, Roald discovered later on that only the top 100 m of the water column was outputted to the PC, resulting in the data for the lower part of the water column being lost.

May 1st

Station 15

ROV dive aborted because transponder of the TMS didn't work.

Station 16

ROV dive aborted because of shortcut in the system. Also, connector cable seems broken. Probably out of service for several days.

Station 17

In situ pumps deployment during strong tide on top of Haas mound. Pump B did not work.

Station 18

Retrieval of ALBEX lander. Difficult retrieval as the weather conditions were not ideal with wind speeds of 30 knots. Particularly difficult as the AEC system was sticking out of the lander on one of the corners. The AEC protective frame got damaged, but sensors and vector were retrieved undamaged. Gradient pump seems to have worked properly as all bags were full.

Station 19

CTD station to link nutrient profile up to the surface ocean. See CTD sheet on public drive.

Station 20

EK500 fish finder station. DvO restarted system at 21.00u en 22.30u. Logging stopped at 23.17u.

May 2nd

Station 21

Long-term mooring on the bank deployed. Followed by triangulation to determine position of the mooring on the seafloor.

Station 22

First boxcore (subcore, i.e. smaller subcore will be taken for incubation in thermocontainer) deployed with video recording (no livestream) on the bank. Limited amount of sediment in the boxcore, because it is a very sandy station. NB: photos were made with 64PE420_21 on the label.

Station 23

Whole boxcore taken from the bank station and placed in incubation bath. Murky water so unclear how deep the sediment is.

Station 24

Boxcore station. Boxcore drained upon recovery. Content checked to decide whether to move to next station. Very sandy, winnowed sediment with drop stones preventing complete closure of boxcore.

Station 25

Boxcore station. Boxcore closed properly with around 12 cm of sediment being collected. We took surface sediment (scraping with a spoon) from a clayish layer that had accumulated on top of the sediment. We also took 2 subcores for incubation and a small core for immediate sectioning for sediment parameters.

Station 26

Deployment of the ALBEX lander on the bank station. Launched without AEC frame, because of risk of losing AEC equipment during retrieval.

Station 27

Test deployment of the ROV. Aborted, because the transponder of the MTS didn't work. Placed on deck again.

Station 28

Second test deployment of the ROV. Aborted because the lights of the ROV didn't work. Placed back on deck, but repair too long for another dive.

Station 29

Deployment of in situ pumps on Bank station at 20mab, +100m (=120mab) and 15mbs. Triggered to run between 2:00 and 6:00 at peak tide.

May 3rd

Station 29, continued

In situ pumps on board. Bottom filter was very full especially the most coarse filter.

ROV dive for the afternoon cancelled because of high swell.

Station 30

CTD station. Particle rich layer is located shallower than evening of May 2nd, but still visible. Decided to go further up the bank to trace the origin of the suspended particles, following a transect along a straight line from Oreo Mound to the Bank station up Rockall Bank.

First transect station selected is 55°40.41N / 15°56.79W

Particle plume is visible on the *fishfinder* (left part of picture), but plume seems to fade during the transect (NB response is not linear and could hence be an attenuation issue) and moving higher up in the water column (right side of picture). However, this profile does not correspond to the CTD downcast, where the deep high turbidity/fluorescence layer is still visible close to the seafloor.

Station 31

CTD station, at water depth of 454m. Although layer seems to be gone in the echosounder, the downcast shows again the high particle layer to around 30 mab. Target for next station is another 2 miles up the bank (55°42.30N / 15°57.70W).

Station 32

CTD station, at water depth of 440 m. Bottom layer gets a bit thinner while surface layer seems to be a better mixed. Decided to move again 2 miles to next station (55°44.30N / 15°58.40W). Shipboard ADCP was switched on for continuous current measurements, but does not operate due to critical missing components of Multibeam system.

Station 33

CTD station. Pattern indicates that water masses are moving in different directions. Surface part of the water column shows random pattern, but bottom water mass seems to dilute away when moving north (up the bank). Next station again 2 miles (55°46.20N / 15°59.20W).

Station 34

CTD station. Again 2-mile step taken, this is last small step. Niskin bottles closed at deepest part of the cast, low oxygen and chlorophyll maximum (3 bottles each). Last station is on the bank, 10 miles away from present station (55°56.13N / 16°02.91W). Bottom layer remains clearly distinct with higher O₂, higher FLUO+TURB, but lower salinity.

Station 35

Last CTD cast along this transect. Station is highest up the bank. Bottom depth is 344 m. Low oxygen zone is not here anymore and the layer with high turbidity and fluorescence is much thinner (<30m) than at start of transect (see figure below).

Station 36

ALBEX-CTD cast with Niskin bottles being closed. Samples collected at bottom, 20mab, 50mab, 100mab, 200mab and in chlorophyll maximum.

Station 37

ALBEX recovery. Gradient pump and MacLane pumps have worked. Filter coloration upon retrieval shows a clear pattern related to the tidal cycle (see figure below).

Station 38-42

CTDs at bank station to capture (part of a) tidal cycle (see preliminary figure below)

Station 43

In situ pumps deployed overnight.

May 4th

Station 43, continued

Successful retrieval of in situ pumps. All pumps worked. Filters of bottom pump full of material.

Short transit to Oreo Mound

Station 44

CTD with Niskin bottles closed at depth to collect incubation water near from Oreo Mound. Double peak observed in the fluorescence (at about 200-meter water depth and hence either DCM or 'sinking' surface material).

Station 45

Boxcore collected for Sandra's incubations. Al lot of sponges, including *Spongisorites*, but no living coral.

Station 46

Second boxcore collected for Sandra's incubations, with living coral and two large crinoids. Samples stored for incubation for O2 and nuts. Not sufficient for material for feeding study.

Station 47

First boxcore collected for whole core incubation. Water is murky upon retrieval so difficult to see what is inside the boxcore, but kept anyway as some coral framework was sticking out at the bottom. Water bath slightly too warm due to sunny day just after placement in the bathtub.

Station 48

Second whole boxcore collected for whole core incubation. Not fully closed at bottom and discarded.

Station 49

ALBEX deployment.

Station 50

ROV dive, reaching bottom and with nice images being made. Sampling proved to be difficult using the ROV arm. Alternatively, a net may be used. ALBEX lander could not be approached, because the forward-looking HD camera was not functioning. After photos and test sampling, the dive was aborted.

Station 51

CTD cast with the in-situ pump station next to Haas mound. Site selected close to the 'old' thermistor site from VanHaren'14 as we know that an internal wave passes this area and corals are abundant at this depth.

May 5th

Station 51, continued

Filters pumped for four hours and were full, but clearly not as much as on the bank station.

Station 52

First boxcore failed. Did not trip.

Station 52

Boxcore surfaced up with big piece of framework and living coral. Unfortunately, the boxcore content was tilted. Living coral pieces were collected by Sandra and framework was kept to determine volume. Decided to take another boxcore here.

Station 53

Boxcore failed: no propulsion.

Station 54

Full boxcore with mostly dead coral framework. Difficult to seal the boxcore, because air keeps creeping in.

Station 55

CTD, start of transect towards Oreo bank.

Station 56,57,58,59,60

CTD transect from below Oreo Mound up to the bank. On station 57 we closed all Niskin bottles at 650m for incubation water for whole boxcore incubations.

No activities during the night. Slow transit only.

May 6th

Station 61

CTD at site of ALBEX deployment with samples being collected from the water column. An additional 9 bottles were closed at the bottom for incubation water.

Station 62

ALBEX lander recovery site. Nice and calm recovery despite waves and wind. Profile pumps have worked and AEC frame is recovered without impacts or damage.

Station 63

Boxcore site for collecting material for incubations on the slope of Haas mound to collect framework for the isotope tracer feeding study with DOM and POM. First boxcore successful in bringing up dead framework. Several Calliostoma specimens and shells. Decided to do one last boxcore to have sufficient material to choose from for labelling study.

Station 64

Boxcore also full of coral framework with sponges and other epifauna. Material used for labeling study.

Station 65

Boxcore from the top of the mound, thin and very degraded framework. Enough for framework incubations.

Station 66

Boxcore from Oreo mound for whole core incubation. Boxcore did trip, but didn't close properly (left picture), possibly because we are on too steep topography. The boxcore did however bring up a large piece of living coral with a crinoid (right photo).

Station 67

Second boxcore from Oreo mound for whole core incubation. Boxcore fired outside the boxcore frame and therefore got stuck. Crew had to partially dismantle the boxcore to fix it again.

Station 68

Moved the ship a little bit to try to move closer to the top of the mound. Boxcore failed, did not trip.

Station 69

Second attempt on the top of the mound. Boxcore failed again, did not trip. Coral fragments between the connectors of the video may suggest that the boxcore is on steep terrain and doesn't hit the seafloor well. On deck, the boxcore fired immediately. Hence, decided to choose a new position on a flatter area next to the mound summit. Video wasn't setup so no visual feedback on deployment.

Station 70

Moved to location just next to the mound top on a relatively flat area for another boxcore try. Now well sealed, but difficult to judge what is in it because the water is murky. Placed in water bath to recover and start of incubation.

Station 71

CTD cast to check water column properties above Oreo mound.

Station 72

In situ pump deployment on the Oreo mound top.

May 7th

Station 72, continue

In situ pumps recovered. Recovery at 7:30 with CTD bottles closed at the bottom for incubation water.

Station 73

Boxcore for whole boxcore incubation from Oreo mound. Taken at similar place as St70 to increase change of successful sampling.

Station 74

ROV dive on Oreo mound with a south-north transect from bottom of mound to top. Pictures below give a representation of the zonation of the mound. At the foot of the mound (± 1000 m deep, left picture), we found a seafloor of coarse sediment with many drop stones, populated by *Cidaris* and some *Aphrocallistes* (deep-sea glass sponge). Many Cutthroat eels were seen swimming 1-2 m above the seafloor. Half-way the mound, at a depth of ± 900 m (middle picture), we found *Styllasterids*, an increased abundance of *Aphrocallistes*, sparse *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata* colonies, some Crinoids and first patches of reef framework. Finally, at the top of the mound (800-750 m, right picture), we found the coral mound to be covered with a high density of Crinoids, a dense framework of live *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata*, a thick cover of dead framework, encrusting sponges. Seen in the picture is also a specimen of ox-eyed Oreo, after which the mound is named.

Station 75

Deployment of the ALBEX lander on Oreo mound with AEC frame attached. Position determined from GAPS transponder is 55 27.2112 N / 015 52.4210 W.

Station 76

Next ROV dive planned on an unexplored, unnamed mound southeast of Oreo mound (see map below). Dive was problematic because of strong currents and had to be aborted before completion because of problems in maneuvering the ROV along the transect. There were many particles and aggregates in the water column which made it difficult to make photographs (reflection). In general, however, the transect gave a comparable view as for Oreo mound.

Station 77

CTD cast just south of Oreo mound to map the water column next to the mound.

Station 78

CTD cast on in situ pump station of Oreo mound to map the water column.

Station 79

In situ pump deployment above Oreo mound (3:00 – 7:00 am pumping). Highly dynamic water column dynamics observed slightly downslope Oreo mound with deep peaks of chlorophyll and even lower density water at depth.

May 8th

Station 79, continued

Recovery of in situ pumps at 7:30. Bottles were accidentally not closed for incubation water.

Station 80-95

CTD transect starting from above Oreo mound up the bank. At station 80, Niskins were closed above Oreo mound for incubation water.

May 9th

Station 96

CTD with water samples (bottom, +20, +50, +100, +200, chl. max) on top of Oreo Mound just before ALBEX recovery to complete the whole nutrient profile up to the water column. Other bottles closed at the bottom for incubation water.

Station 97

Recovery of ALBEX lander from Oreo mound.

Station 98

Deployment of long-term mooring from Oreo mound. Placed around 11.00u. Triangulation shows that the LT mooring landed within 70 meter of the target point.

	latitude		longitude		MB depth	latdec	longdec	range	cor.range	model	squares
	deg	min	deg	min	m			m	m	m	
deployment	55	27.000	015	52.100	750	55.4500	15.8683	750	750	67	
point 1	55	27.237	015	51.416		55.4540	15.8569	1160	1160	1162	3
point 2	55	26.582	015	52.013		55.4430	15.8669	1140	1140	1142	2
point 3	55	27.206	015	52.784		55.4534	15.8797	1080	1080	1082	4
point 4						0.0000	0.0000		0	0	0
point 5						0.0000	0.0000		0	0	0
point 6						0.0000	0.0000		0	0	0
point 7						0.0000	0.0000		0	0	0
X	55	27.025	015	52.146	781	55.4504	15.8691			sumsquar	9
distance from calculated position to deployment position in m:								67			

Station 99

Recovery of thermistor string from the flank of Haas mound.

Station 100-111

CTD yo-yo's just south of Oreo mound to follow water dynamics above the reef. Bottom water from station 100 was taken for a control (i.e. only seawater) whole boxcore incubation.

Station 112

CTD drop directly following the previous CTD yo-yo, with in situ pumps installed on the line.

May 10th

Station 112, continued

Recovery of the in situ pumps.

Station 113-115

CTD yo-yo casts, continuation of stations 100-111.

Transit to Galway

End of cruise

3. ALBEX lander

Furu Mienis and Gerard Duineveld

During cruise 64PE420 an ALBEX lander was deployed for short term duration (1-2 days) at different sites amidst the corals growing on the slope of Rockall Bank and at a site higher up the bank (Fig. 3.1 and 3.2). Main goal of these short-term lander deployments was to measure variability in near-bed environmental conditions (water-reef interface). We hypothesize that the reef influences the near-bed current flow, while on the other hand the flow of water will influence the exchange of inorganic nutrients, food supply and oxygen content of water in between the coral framework.

The ALBEX lander is basically an aluminium tripod equipped with 13 glass Benthos floats, two IXSEA acoustic releasers and a single 250 kg ballast weight necessary for deployment and recovery. For ease of recovery a satellite beacon, radio beacon, flash light and large orange flag were attached to the frame. Furthermore, the lander was equipped with an Aquadopp current sensor to measure current direction and speed, and a Rinko optode to measure near-bottom oxygen concentrations. Both sensors were mounted in the frame at 1 m above the bottom. An AEC system of the University of South Denmark was also added to the frame (see chapter 4).

To measure the variability in particle load through time a McLane particle pump was mounted in the frame, which contains 24 filter cups. The system was pre-programmed to pump 10 L of water over pre-weighed GFF filters at 2 hour intervals. The inlet of the pumped system was situated at 40 cm above the seafloor. Filters collected with this system were retrieved and immediately stored at -80 °C. At NIOZ these filters will be analysed for organic carbon, nitrogen, C and N isotopes and pigments. In addition, a newly designed NIOZ made profile pump was attached to the frame. This profile pump has 6 inlets that are mounted at different depths above the bottom and water is pumped into 6-L sampling bags to measure the gradient in particle content as well as geochemical properties of the water just above the reef. Water samples collected with the profile pump have been sub sampled for inorganic nutrients, DOC, DIC and bacteria counts. Up to 5 L of water is filtered over pre-weighed GFF filters to analyse the organic carbon and nitrogen content.

During the cruise, the lander was first deployed at the summit of Haas mound for 1.5 days. After recovery, the lander was deployed at the shallow Rockall Bank. This time without the AEC system. The last two deployments were made at the southern foot of Haas mound and on the summit of Oreo mound.

Fig. 3.1 Deployment of Landers on Haas Mound

Fig. 3.2 Deployment of landers on Oreo mound

4. Aquatic eddy covariance

Lorenzo Rovelli

In order to quantify the dissolve oxygen (O_2) uptake by the cold-water coral communities an Aquatic Eddy Co-variance (AEC) system from the University of Southern Denmark was deployed together with the ALBEX lander on Haas mound and Oreo mound. As it was shown by e.g., Cathalot et al. (2015) and Rovelli et al. (2015), the AEC technique provides estimates of benthic metabolism over areas up to 80 m^2 , which cannot be covered by traditional methods (e.g., benthic chambers and core incubations), and does not alter the local hydrodynamics and food supply making it a powerful tool to investigate the metabolism of CWC communities.

Deployment setup

The AEC system consisted of a deep-sea rated acoustic Doppler velocimeter (ADV Vector, Nortek), underwater amplifier (see McGinnis et al. 2011) with two fast Clark-type O_2 microsensors (Fig. 4.1) and a dedicated battery canister. This self-contained setup enabled up to 5 days of continuous sampling at 64 Hz. The AEC system was mounted on one the ALBEX lander legs using aluminum brackets and protected by an aluminum cage (Fig. 4.1). The ADV sampling volume was positioned at a measurement height (h) of 80 – 86 cm, and thus higher than bottom features, such as live coral patches, to prevent avoid potential flow disturbances and to minimize the risk of sensor breakage (Fig. 4.2).

Figure 4.1. Aquatic eddy covariance system mounted on the ALBEX lander. Left: ALBEX lander with being deployed at the Haas Mound (AEC-01). Right: Close-up of the ADV and O_2 microsensors.

Figure 4.2. Aquatic eddy covariance equipment and principle of operation. The measurement height (h) indicates the distance between the bottom and the velocimeter sampling volume (yellow cylinder). The theoretical size of the footprint depends on h and the local bottom roughness.

The AEC was deployed a total of 3 times yielding 110 h of measurements (Table 4.1). The first deployment (station 64PE420_7, AEC-01) was performed at the summit of Haas mound where previous surveys have indicated a dominance of coral rubble and sparse patches of live corals and generally reduced flow. The lander retrieval occurred during conditions of strong wind and swell, which complicated the procedure. The AEC system suffered moderate damage, mainly to the ADV, and the original protection cage was severely damaged due to the lander colliding with the ship on retrieval. It was therefore decided to skip the next ALBEX lander deployment (station 64PE420_26 – Bank reference) to assess the damage and design a more efficient cage. The reinforced AEC system was redeployed on the 3rd ALBEX lander deployment (station 64PE420_49, AEC-02) on the flank of Haas mound, where previous surveys have indicated extensive occurrence of live coral patches. As the flow velocities over the flanks were expected to be higher than at the summit of the mound, the AEC setting were tuned accordingly (Table 4.2). The final AEC deployment was performed at the summit of the smaller Oreo mound (station 64PE420_75, AEC-03), where extensive live coral patches were also previously reported. The ALBEX lander landed strongly tilted (20° of pitch), but was that did not cause apparent problems to the lander operations or retrieval.

Table 4.1. Overview of Aquatic Eddy covariance deployments

AEC	Site	Coordinates	Depth	Start	Collected data (h)
[Station]	[Location]	(N° / W°)	(m)	(Date UTC)	
AEC-01	Haas Mound	55° 29.20332'	536	30. Apr 2017	28
[64PE420_7]	[Summit]	15° 47.99460'		13:00:00	
AEC-02	Haas Mound	55° 29.2053'	738	4. May 2017	41
[64PE420_49]	[Flank]	15° 48.20358'		16:00:00	
AEC-03	Oreo Mound	55° 27.211'	745	7. May 2017	41*
[64PE420_75]	[Summit]	15° 52.421'		15:00:00	

*: one microsensor broke after 3 h of deployment.

Table 4.2 Specific AEC deployment settings

AEC	Sampling rate (Hz)	Nominal velocity* (m s ⁻¹)	Common ADV settings	<i>h</i> ** (m)
AEC-01	64	±0.3	Continuous sampling,	0.80
AEC-02	64	±1.0	XYZ coordinates, power level high, salinity 35 PSU	0.86
AEC-03	64	±1.0		0.86

*: The resolvable horizontal velocity range is 0.81 m s⁻¹ and 2.1 m s⁻¹ for a nominal velocity of 0.3 m s⁻¹ and 1.0 m s⁻¹, respectively (see Nortek Vector manual).

** : The measurement height (*h*) was estimated on deck prior to deployment.

Preliminary results

During the AEC-01 deployment at the summit of Haas mound, flow velocities were up to 40 cm s⁻¹, and displayed a well-developed tidal ellipsoid (Fig. 4.3 top-left). The orientation of the AEC system was diagonal to the main tidal axis, with the lander shadow potentially affecting the measurements only during a total period of 7 hours (i.e. 25% of the measurements). This was also observed in the particle track (Fig. 4.3 top-right). At the flank of Haas mound (AEC-02), the flow regime was more complex and characterized by high flow velocities, which peaked at 2 m s⁻¹ (Fig. 4.3 center-left). At least 14 h of measurements are presumed to be affected by the lander shadow (i.e. 35% of the measurements). Similar flow dynamics were observed on the summit of Oreo mound (AEC-03),

though the velocities were less scattered and strongly directional (Fig. 4.3 bottom-left and bottom-right).

Figure 4.3. Flow velocities and theoretical particle track during AEC-01 (top), AEC-02 (center) and AEC-03 (bottom). Left: scatter plot of flow velocities in instrument coordinates. Positive values indicate flows directed towards the ADV. The data were averaged to 10 s to highlight the main flow contributions. Directions where the flow was potentially obstructed by the lander (i.e., lander shadow) are indicated by the grey sector. Right: Horizontal particle track

based on instrument coordinates and 1 min velocities averages. The color scale refers to the hours of deployment from the beginning of the deployment day (00:00 UTC, see Table 4.1).

The high flow velocities and instrument tilt during the AEC-02 and AEC-03 deployments caused conflicts with the existing AEC processing routines as they represent boarder conditions for the applicability of the AEC technique. Thus, estimates of O_2 fluxes are only presented here for AEC-01 (Fig. 4.4). The preliminary fluxes were mostly negative with rates up to $115 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $30 - 40 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ on average. The occasional positive fluxes were mostly attributed to lander shadow an, transient O_2 concentration changes (i.e., O_2 storage), though further analysis will be required to validates the assess the quality of each hourly average and flag artifacts.

Figure 4.4. Preliminary dataset from AEC-01 (Station 7 - summit of Haas mound). Deployment time is in hours after 30. Apr 00:00 UTC. a) Hydrostatic pressure. b) Flow velocity in ADV coordinates. Negative velocities indicate flow going towards the ADV. c) Dissolved oxygen concentrations during the deployment. d) Hourly-averaged of dissolved oxygen fluxes (with standard error bars). Note that the O_2 concentration were calibrated in lab conditions and thus both O_2 time series and fluxes are to be considered preliminary. All time series were average to 10 min to better highlight the dominant trends.

Further work

The current AEC processing protocols (Attard et al. 2014; Rovelli et al. 2015) will need to be modified to account for the large flow velocities observed during AEC-02 and AEC-03 deployments and the strong tilt of the instrument. The collected datasets will generally require further screening to filter out time interval with suboptimal flow directions based on velocity scatter plots and particle tracks (Fig. 4.3). The O₂ microsensors readings will be fine-tuned with the in situ O₂ measurements from the ALBEX lander to provide a more robust calibration. O₂ measurements will also be used to quantify and account for the storage of O₂ between the sea bottom and the measurement height (h). This effect has been shown to bias AEC-based benthic fluxes (e.g., Holtappels et al., 2013; Rheuban et al., 2014) and is expected to be significant for the collected datasets given the relatively high h (Table 4.2). The theoretical size of the AEC footprint for each deployment will also be estimated prior to the interpretation of the O₂ uptake rates. These rates are planned to be compared and traditional methods (e.g. box-core incubations) and discussed within a “gradient” of CWC communities from the mound summit to the flanks. As visual inspection of the AEC footprint areas was not possible during the cruise, the communities will be characterized indirectly based on the known ALBEX lander deployment locations and previous surveys of the investigated sites.

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5. Boxcores and sediment subcore incubations

Evert de Froe

During this cruise, whole boxcore incubation were conducted at seven stations from three different locations: Haas mound, Oreo mound, and up Rockall bank. The goal of these experiments was to obtain a robust measure of metabolic activity and nutrient consumption/excretion of the reef framework and compare between different locations. Additionally, we want to compare metabolic activity of the whole framework with results of incubation experiments with parts of the reef (as in (Cathalot et al., 2015)).

The boxcores were taken with the Haja boxcoring developed by NIOZ. The boxcorer consists of a stainless-steel framework on which a boxcore with heavy weights and a cutting blade is constructed.

The boxcorer is lowered into the ocean and travels with a speed of 60 meter per minute to the bottom. Then, with help of a mechanical mechanism, boxcore is pushed into the surface of the ocean bottom by the heavy weights and closed off from the bottom with the cutting blade. The boxcore is then pulled on deck. Fig. 5.1 shows the boxcorer on deck after taking a boxcore. The dimensions of the boxcore are 50 cm diameter and 55 cm in height, meaning each boxcore samples roughly 0.2 m² of seafloor.

Figure 5.1. The Haja boxcorer after sampling

After the collection of the boxcore, the top of the core was closed off with a plexi glass lid to prevent leakage of the overlaying water and to minimize disturbance. The lid was closed airtight with screws and bolts and ambient seawater, earlier retrieved with the CTD, was added to top off the boxcore with seawater. The boxcore was placed in a cooling bath to maintain the temperature to in-situ conditions. Figure 5.2 shows a picture of the boxcore just before lifting it into the cooling bath. Note the core is already closed off with a lid and filled completely with seawater. After the core was placed in the cooling bath, a stirrer, oxygen sensor and temperature sensor were placed in the lid of the boxcore. A black non-transparent cover was used to ensure dark conditions during the incubation.

After an acclimatization period of at least one hour, the incubation was started by taking DIC, DOC, nutrient and alkalinity samples. At the end of the incubation, the same samples were taken and, if feasible, also water samples were taken in between the start and the end of the incubation. After the incubation, the boxcore was lifted out of its cooling bath. The macrofaunal community was sampled, and sediment samples were taken for sediment characteristics and pigment analysis. Subsequently, water volume, living coral, and dead framework volume were estimated and the boxcore was sieved up to 500 mm mesh size.

Figure 5.2. Picture of the boxcore just before being lifted into its cooling bath.

A total of 7 whole boxcores were successfully incubated from the study area (Fig. 5.3) and two boxcores from the Bank station were subsampled for subcore incubations (Table 5.1). Figures 5.4 and 5.5 show boxcore locations (successful and unsuccessful) on Haas Mound and Oreo Mound, respectively.

Table 1: Overview of stations where boxcores were taken.

Station	Type of incubation	Location	Quick characteristics
5	Whole boxcore	Haas mound	Mainly dead framework, water stayed murky whole incubation
6	Whole boxcore	Haas mound	Large pieces of <i>L. pertusa</i> along with macrofaunal as shrimps, swimming crab. Showed highest respiration.
22	Subsample boxcore	Rockall bank	Subsample core of mainly sandy sediment.
23	Whole boxcore	Rockall bank	Whole boxcore of sandy sediment. Water stayed murky whole incubation.
25	Subsample boxcore (2x)	Rockall bank	Two subsample cores out of one boxcore. Also sandy sediment
47	Whole boxcore	Haas mound	Small pieces of <i>L. pertusa</i> and <i>M. oculata</i>
54	Whole boxcore	Haas mound	Full of dead framework. Hardly any sediment and living coral.
70	Whole boxcore	Oreo mound	Large pieces of <i>M. oculata</i> .
73	Whole boxcore	Oreo mound	Contained pieces of <i>M. oculata</i> .

Figure 5.3. Boxcore locations from the whole study area

Figure 5.4. Boxcore locations from Haas Mound only.

Figure 5.4. Boxcore locations from Ore Mound.

Preliminary results

The oxygen saturation curves of three incubations shows that respiration seems to be higher in boxcores with framework compared to boxcores with only sediment. Figure 5.6 shows the percentage of oxygen air saturation of the boxcores from station 6, 23 and 73 (Table 5.1). The oxygen saturation increases first at station 23, which is probably due to problems with keeping the incubation core airtight. In several cores, difficulties were encountered in keeping the boxcore airtight (Fig. 5.7). To counter this, we kept the water level of the cooling water at the same height as the top of the incubation core. To prevent water exchange between the incubation water and the cooling water, water sampling occurred through tubing that was connected to the core lid. The openings of the incubation lid must be completely closed to prevent exchange from happening.

Figure 5.6. Percentage of oxygen air saturation in three boxcores. Station 6 = Haas mound, station 23 = Rockall bank, station 73 = Ore mound

Figure 6: Air bubble can be seen in the middle of the conically shaped lid.

7. ROV Genesis

Wim Versteeg

The Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) "Genesis" is a 2000m depth-rated CHEROKEE ROV with a Tether Management System (TMS) built by the company Sub-Atlantic. It was acquired by the "Renard Centre of Marine Geology" of the University of Ghent and later donated to the VLIZ, which ensures

the management and the operations of the ROV. The ROV-system was totally renewed (hydraulic winch, control-container, HD cameras and LED-lights) in 2016.

In this TMS-mode a winch with an umbilical of 1600m is used to lower the ROV from the ship's deck to 20-30m above the seafloor within the TMS-cage. The ROV can then freely survey the seafloor connected to the TMS with a tether cable of 200m.

Positioning on a meter-scale and navigation of the ROV was achieved with an IXBLUE GAPS-system and ROV-mounted and TMS-mounted transponders. The calibration-free Global Acoustic Positioning System (GAPS) is a portable Ultra Short Base Line (USBL) with integrated Inertial Navigation System (INS) and Global Position System (GPS). The GAPS was attached and deployed from an over-the-side pole on the port side of the RV Pelagia. It also used the ships onboard GPS-signal. An additional transponder was used to get an accurate position of the ALBEX-lander. Real-time positions of ship, ROV and TMS were displayed on screen during ROV-operations by the GAPS-software.

ROV in TMS-cage

Recovery of ROV-system

ROV control-room

Overview of ROV dives during this cruise

Station 7: ROV-Dive cancelled due to bad weather conditions

Station 15: ROV-Dive1 stopped at 100m depth due to no reception of TMS-transponder
Replacement of the transponder

Station 16: ROV-Dive2 cancelled at 250m depth due to a shortcut in 3000V-circuit
Caused by one of the 5000V connectors; need to be replaced
No dive within the next hours

Station 27 ROV-Dive3 stopped at 100m depth; no reception of TMS-transponder
Changed frequency of this transponder (f4 ->f2)

Station 28 ROV-Dive4 cancelled at 150m depth; no Led-lights
Repairs too long for next deployment
Caused by blown of an OpAmp on the dimmer-board

Station 29 ROV-dive cancelled due to big swell

Station 50 ROV-Dive5 at the bottom at 55° 29.19 N, 15° 48.20W and 1056m depth

After 45 seconds HD-camera, Low-Light camera and Sonar down

Some stills and sampling with manipulator tests were done. Sampling proved to be difficult using the ROV arm. At 250m depth recovery of the equipment which indicated a pressure problem.

Station 74 ROV-Dive6 at bottom: 10:43u 55°26.42N, 15°51.98W, 1036m

from bottom: 12:32u 55°27.11N, 15°52.25W, 748m

LowLight-camera stopped at 600m depth (caused previous failure)

Very nice trajectory over the Oreo-mound (Stills & HD-video)

Station 76 ROV-Dive7 at bottom: 16:00u 55°25.04N, 15°55.55W, 1038m

from bottom: 17:13u 55°25.49N, 15°55.68W, 836m

Trajectory over unnamed mount southeast of Oreo-mound

Dive was problematic because of high currents from eastern direction and had to be stopped before completion because of problems in maneuvering the ROV along the transect. (Stills & HD-video)

After these dives, the umbilical was damaged near the bullet of TMS-cage. There were 20 of the 40 coated steel wires of the outer layer broken and loose. Another dive was impossible and re-termination of this umbilical would take too much time.

8. Coral and fauna incubations

Sandra Maier

When cold-water corals (CWC) grow towards the food-delivering currents, they leave behind a thick layer of tissue-barren coral skeletons, which, enforced by sediment trapping a. o. forms the coral mounds of Rockall Bank. This matrix of dead coral skeleton, henceforth called 'framework', offers substrate and shelter for many associated species and represents that part of the CWC reef with the highest biodiversity. Little is known about the food requirements, metabolic activity and nutrient cycling of this framework community, and its contribution to the overall reef productivity.

The metabolic activity and food requirements of the reef framework was assessed in two on-board experimental approaches:

1. Framework incubations
2. Feeding study using stable isotope tracers

1. Framework incubations

Video footage from Haas mound has shown that corals thrive mainly at the side of the mound, while the summit largely consists of dead coral framework and sediment. Further, boxcore samples shows a clear difference in the degradation state of the framework, with 'older' framework being darker brown in coloration (Fig. 1).

Chamber incubations were used to assess (a) the difference in framework metabolic activity, OM and nutrient cycling between the side and the summit of Haas mound, and (b) the influence of the framework degradation state on its metabolic activity.

Figure 8.1. More degraded framework (left) versus less degraded framework (right) in an incubation chamber.

We planned for a 2-factor experimental design:

However, only old framework was encountered on the summit of Haas mound, forcing us to leave out the factor combination ‘summit-less degraded framework’.

Site	OF/NF	n	Fluxes
Haas side	OF	3	O ₂ , DIC, nutrients, DOM, POM
	NF	3	
Haas summit	OF	3	
	NF	na	

OF= old, i.e. more degraded framework; NF = new, i.e. less degraded framework; DIC = dissolved inorganic carbon, nutrients = NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻; DOM & POM = dissolved and particulate organic matter.

Incubations were carried out for 48 h in the dark in a thermo-container that was set to the in-situ temperature of 9°C. Pieces of framework were placed into 4.8L airtight incubations chambers, equipped with magnetic stirrers to avoid concentration gradients and a Firesting optode to continuously record O₂ concentration. To assess dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), nutrient and dissolved organic matter (DOM) fluxes, water samples were taken at the beginning of the incubation (t₀), after 24h (t₁) and after 48h (t₂). Water samples for particulate OM (POM) were taken at t₀ and

t2. Incubations without framework served to control for microbial activity in the incubation water and potential contaminations. Water samples were fixed and stored frozen/cooled for analysis at NIOZ.

Preliminary results on respiration data for suggest a higher oxygen consumption for less degraded framework; nevertheless, since respiration rates are not yet standardized to dry mass or carbon, data do not yet allow final conclusion.

Figure 3.2. Respiration rates of less degraded framework ('less') versus more degraded framework ('more'). Respiration rates are in $\mu\text{mol O}_2 \text{ h}^{-1}$ and are corrected for O_2 fluxes in seawater control incubations.

2. Feeding study with stable isotopes

In the feeding study, stable isotope tracers were used to assess the relative importance of dissolved and particulate organic matter as food sources for the framework-associated community.

A dissolved and particulate food substrate was used in the feeding study. The diatom *Skeletonema marinoi* was grown beforehand on a ^{13}C and ^{15}N -enriched medium to enrich them in the heavy stable isotopes of carbon and nitrogen. Lyophilized diatoms served as (a) particulate food source, and (b) dissolved organic matter was extracted from the diatoms via osmolysis of cells and $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ -filtration.

Framework was collected from the side of Haas mound in two boxcores and sorted into 'more' and 'less' degraded pieces. One piece of each was combined into experimental framework units (Fig. 8.2). Three combinations of old and new framework pieces (referred to as "framework") were fed with ^{13}C - and ^{15}N -enriched POM, another three with ^{13}C - and ^{15}N -enriched DOM, in incubation chambers for three times 12h. Water samples were taken at the start and the end of each feeding interval for POM/DOM to determine ingestion of the respective food source. Food was also added to two 'control chambers' without framework ($n=2$ per food source) to control for microbial activity in the seawater and procedural errors.

Figure 8.2. Combinations of new and old framework pieces to experimental "framework" units (n=6).

After the last feeding interval, chambers were flushed to remove left-over food, closed air-tight, and the framework incubated for 20h to measure respiration from continuous O₂ recording with Firesting optodes. Nutrient and OM fluxes will be determined from water samples taken at the start and the end of the incubation. The same measurements were also carried out on the control chambers. Water samples were fixed and stored for analysis at NIOZ.

After the experiment, fauna associated with the framework was sorted to lowest ID possible, and stored frozen for analysis of carbon, nitrogen and isotopic composition at NIOZ.

9. Thermistor string

Dick van Oevelen

The thermistor string was deployed at the side of Haas Mound. After deployment, the position was checked using the response function of the releases and triangulation:

	latitude		longitude		MB depth	latdec	longdec	
	deg	min	deg	min	m			
deployment	55	29.870	015	46.990	640	55.4978	15.7832	
point 1	55	29.760	015	47.956		55.4960	15.7993	1320
point 2	55	30.156	015	46.713		55.5026	15.7786	909
point 3	55	29.595	015	46.559		55.4933	15.7760	900
triangulated position	55	29.848	015	46.889	685	55.4975	15.7815	
	distance from calculated position to deployment position in m:							114

The top-buoy of the thermistor string held a ‘down-looking’ Teledyne/RDI 75 kHz, four beam acoustic Doppler current profiler (ADCP). It measures currents in three directions, $U = [u, v, w]$, and echo intensity in each beam at 84 vertical bins of 5 m. The ADCP stores data once per minute.

The string was further equipped with NIOZ4 self-contained T-sensors that sample at 1 Hz, with a sensor tip smaller than 1 mm, a precision better than $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ after drift-correction and a noise level of $< 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. They measure at a rate of once per s.

10. Long-term moorings

Gerard Duineveld

Two long term moorings were deployed during the cruise i.e. one on the shallow part of Rockall Bank (~450 m water depth, st21) and the other one deeper on the slope of Rockall Bank on top of a coral mound (~795 m water depth, st98). The lower 50 m of both moorings were similarly configured and are composed of (from bottom to top): anchor, 2 acoustic releasers, Wetlabs FLNTU & Aquadopp profiler (downward looking), Technicap PPS4/3 sediment trap (HgCl preserved), buoyancy smartie with 75 KHz ADCP (upward looking). The deeper mooring had an extension of 310 m wire with a second Wetlabs FLNTU attached at 425 m above bottom.

Figure 10.1. Configuration of bottom 50 m part of long-term moorings. One mooring had an additional extension of ~300 m.

The two moorings were configured and positioned in order to record near any near-bottom cross-slope advection of organic matter from the shallow bank towards the deeper coral mounds. The occurrence of such advection was inferred from earlier records of fluorescence and temperature measured on top of coral mounds in 2006. A recently proposed explanation for the energy supply of the coral mounds is vertical downwelling of surface primary production over the mounds induced by the interaction of internal waves with the local topography (lee-waves). To record downwelling, the deepest mooring had an additional turbidity-fluorescence sensor at 425 m above bottom. The two moorings are to be recovered after 1 year.

11. CTD, 24 hour stations and sensor calibration

Gerard Duineveld, Dick van Oevelen, Furu Mienis, Lorenzo Rovelli and Gert-Jan Reichart

Using a conductivity-temperature-depth (CTD) equipped with a go-flow rosette sampler the water column structure at all CTD stations was analyzed and some depths were sampled. Generally, 5 depths were sampled, with special emphasis on the layers with higher turbidity. The sensors on the CTD collected continuous profiles of key physicochemical water column properties: conductivity, temperature, fluorescence, beam transmission and dissolved O₂, the latter with a Seabird oxygen electrode, and turbidity using an extra mounted OBS. The sea-bird oxygen sensor was not functioning properly and exchanged after station 3. The water collected in the CTD bottles at various depths was immediately sampled and stored for NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, PO₄³⁻, and Si analyses at the home laboratory (Appendix 1).

Figures of the CTD casts, CTD transects and CTD yoyo's are given below, as well as overview maps with respective station numbers.

64PE420 - Station 02

64PE420 - Station 03

64PE420 - Station 17

64PE420 - Station 19

64PE420 - Station 30

Transect from Oreo mount to Rockal Bank (stations 80-95)

Transect from Oreo mount to Rockall Bank (stations 80-95)

Transect from Oreo mount to Rockall Bank (stations 80-95)

CTD yoyo at Oreo mount (stations 100-111).

CTD yoyo at Oreo mount (stations 100-111).

CTD yoyo at Oreo mount (stations 100-111).

CTD stations, overview

CTD Haas sea mound

CTD Oreo sea mound

12. In-situ pumps

Sabena Blackbird

Figure 1, A) In-situ pump being deployed on the CTD line, and B) schematic representation of WTS-LV in-situ pump.

McLane Large Volume Water Transfer System Sampler (WTS-LV) in-situ pumps (McLane Research Laboratories Inc., East Falmouth, MA, USA, Figure 1) were deployed at stations at Haas Mound, Bank and Oreo Mound at three depths in the water column (usually) 20mab, 120mab and 15mbs. The depths were chosen according to the fluorescence profile, as around the deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM), at the surface and in between the two.

Each pump was programmed using Crosscut Version 1.0.3 for Windows before deployment. The programming consists of a sample volume nominally set to 2000L; an initial flow rate 7000ml/min; a

minimum flow rate automatically set by Crosscut to 4000ml/min; a time limit 4hrs; the pump data collection period every 1min and a count-down timer.

The in-situ pumps filtered up to 1400 L of water through an acid-washed 50 μm nylon mesh before a pre-ashed glass fibre filter (GF/F) with a nominal pore-size of 0.7 μm collecting the suspended particulate organic matter (sPOM).

The mesh and filters were processed immediately after the pumps were retrieved. The 0.7 μm filter was photographed from above. The filter was carefully folded once, wrapped in aluminium foil and stored at -20°C . Coarse material $>50 \mu\text{m}$ collected on mesh was then filtered through vacuum manifold onto 47mm GF/F 0.7 μm . These filters were placed between aluminium foil in a petri dish and again and stored at -20°C .

In the laboratories of the School of Environmental Sciences, University of Liverpool we will further investigate these two size fractions of the sPOM using a variety of instrumental techniques to gain a greater understanding of the food resources available to the CWCs. This may include relatively unaltered fresh phytoplankton sPOM as well as reworked material forced into the water column through tidal dynamics.

Particulate organic carbon and particulate nitrogen concentrations and molar C/N ratios will be determined via Elemental Analysis (EA). The organic chemical composition (quality) will be assessed by quantitative determination of lipid biological markers such as polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), alcohols, sterols etc. using Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS). Further compound specific isotope analysis of the lipids will involve Isotope Ratio – Mass Spectrometry (IR-MS)

In-situ Pump Filter Photographs

Station3

Station13

Station17

Station29

St29 PumpC loaded mesh!

Station43

Station51

Station 72

Station 79

Station 112

In-situ Pump Data

LOCATION	STATION	TIDE	DEPTH	PUMP	PUMP GAUGE VOL START	PUMP GAUGE VOL END	GAUGE VOL LITRES	CROSSCUT VOL LITRES	TIME PUMPING SECS	TIME PUMPING HRS / MINS	EVENT START	EVENT END	BATTERY START / TEMP	BATTERY END / TEMP	LOWEST BATTERY UNDER LOAD	NOTES
Haas Mound	3	Slack	15m	A	00066245	00066588	343	358.53	4891	1hr 21min	04/29/17 23:07:15	04/30/17 00:28:48	38.1 Vb 11 °C	31.8 Vb 16 °C	26.9 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Haas Mound	3	Slack	75m	B	00097847	00098404	557	733.76	9717	2hr 42min	04/29/17 23:02:35	04/30/17 01:44:33	38.4 Vb 11 °C	29.3 Vb 18 °C	20.5 Vb	Low Battery
Haas Mound	3	Slack	520m	C	00077775	00079410	1635	1407.47	14401	4hr	04/29/17 23:08:19	04/30/17 03:08:21	38.5 Vb 9 °C	30.6 Vb 16 °C	26.3 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Haas Mound	13	Slack	15m	A	00066594	00067022	428	444.9	6231	1hr 44min	04/30/17 17:59:01	04/30/17 19:42:54	38.6 Vb 11 °C	31.1 Vb 16 °C	25.7 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Haas Mound	13	Slack	420m	B	00098405	00099928	1523	1407.46	14400	4hr	04/30/17 18:00:39	04/30/17 22:00:41	38.7 Vb 10 °C	29.6 Vb 15 °C	23.3 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Haas Mound	13	Slack	520m	C	00079415	00080968	1553	1407.46	14401	4hr	04/30/17 17:58:28	04/30/17 21:58:30	38.6 Vb 10 °C	29.5 Vb 16 °C	23.7 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Haas Mound	17	Strong	15m	A	00067023	00067253	230	233.67	3330	0hr 55min	05/01/17 12:00:13	05/01/17 12:55:45	35.2 Vb 11 °C	30.1 Vb 16 °C	23.7 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Haas Mound	17	Strong	420m	B	00099929	00099929	0	0	0		05/01/17 12:00:40	05/01/17 12:00:41	7.5 Vb 10 °C	7.6 Vb 10 °C		Low Battery, see * below
Haas Mound	17	Strong	520m	C	00080971	00082518	1547	1407.46	14401	4hr	05/01/17 11:58:03	05/01/17 15:58:05	38.6 Vb 10 °C	29.4 Vb 16 °C	23.2 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Bank	29	Strong	15m	A	00067256	00067539	283	298.23	4089	1hr 8min	05/03/17 02:02:10	05/03/17 03:10:21	38.2 Vb 10 °C	32.1 Vb 16 °C	27.2 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Bank	29	Strong	360m	B	00099929	00101397	1468	1399.71	14401	4hr	05/03/17 02:00:59	05/03/17 06:01:01	38.4 Vb 10 °C	29.1 Vb 15 °C	21.9 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Bank	29	Strong	460m	C	00082519	00084008	1489	1377.11	14401	4hr	05/03/17 01:59:23	05/03/17 05:59:25	38.4 Vb 9 °C	29.2 Vb 16 °C	22.2 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Bank	43	Strong	15m	A	00067539	00067786	247	255.85	3543	59min	05/04/17 02:45:25	05/04/17 03:44:30	35.7 Vb 10 °C	30.7 Vb 16 °C	25.0 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Bank	43	Strong	360m	B	00101398	00102820	1422	1336.79	13957	3hr 53min	05/04/17 02:46:05	05/04/17 06:38:43	36.5 Vb 10 °C	26.8 Vb 15 °C	20.5 Vb	Low Battery
Bank	43	Strong	460m	C	00084013	00085289	1276	1251.94	14401	4hr	05/04/17 02:45:30	05/04/17 06:45:32	38.3 Vb 9 °C	29.0 Vb 17 °C	21.4 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Off Haas Mound	51	Strong	15m	A	00067787	00067977	190	200.21	2871	48min	05/05/17 03:29:46	05/05/17 04:17:39	35.7 Vb 11 °C	30.8 Vb 16 °C	25.2 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Off Haas Mound	51	Strong	550m	B	00102820	00104354	1534	1405.82	14401	4hr	05/05/17 03:30:20	05/05/17 07:30:22	36.8 Vb 10 °C	28.3 Vb 14 °C	22.4 Vb	Time Limit Reached

Off Haas Mound	51	Strong	650m	C	00085294	00086818	1524	1393.92	14401	4hr	05/05/17 03:30:09	05/05/17 07:30:11	36.7 Vb 10 °C	28.3 Vb 15 °C	21.9 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Oreo Mound	72	Strong	15m	A	00067977	00068087	110	113.98	1624	27min	05/07/17 03:02:15	05/07/17 03:29:21	35.0 Vb 11 °C	30.6 Vb 15 °C	24.4 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Oreo Mound	72	Strong	630m	B	00104355	00105886	1531	1402.93	14401	4hr	05/07/17 03:00:05	05/07/2017 07:00	36.7 Vb 10 °C	28.2 Vb 14 °C	22.1 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Oreo Mound	72	Strong	730m	C	00086819	00088412	1593	1407.46	14401	4hr	05/07/17 03:00:32	05/07/2017 07:00	36.4 Vb 9 °C	28.4 Vb 15 °C	23.1 Vb	Time Limit Reached
Oreo Mound	79	Strong	15m	A	00068088	00068241	153	162.73	2176	36min	05/08/17 02:59:22	05/08/17 03:35:40	38.4 Vb 11 °C	33.5 Vb 16 °C	28.7 Vb	Min Flow Reached
Oreo Mound	79	Strong	630m	B	00105889	00106986	1097	989.81	10160	2hr 49min	05/08/17 03:01:15	05/08/17 05:50:36	35.8 Vb 10 °C	28.0 Vb 14 °C	21.0 Vb	Low Battery
Oreo Mound	79	Strong	730m	C	00088417	00089932	1515	1383.8	14401	4hr	05/08/17 02:59:26	05/08/17 06:59:28	36.5 Vb 9 °C	27.9 Vb 15 °C	21.1 Vb	Time Limit Reached
5th Oreo Mound	112	Strong	15m	A	00068242	00068281	39	41.1	529	9 min	05/10/17 03:45:54	05/10/17 03:54:45	37.3 Vb 11 °C	34.7 Vb 14 °C	29.3 Vb	Min Flow Reached
5th Oreo Mound	112	Strong	630m	B	00106987	00108503	1516	1407.46	14401	4hr	05/10/17 03:45:11	05/10/17 07:45:13	38.4 Vb 9 °C	29.8 Vb 15 °C	24.4 Vb	Time Limit Reached
5th Oreo Mound	112	Strong	730m	C	00089934	00091540	1606	1407.47	14401	4hr	05/10/17 03:44:08	05/10/17 07:44:10	38.3 Vb 9 °C	30.5 Vb 16 °C	26.2 Vb	Time Limit Reached

* Batteries had been replaced prior to deployment and read 38.6 Vb in Crosscut diagnostics. Pumps failed due to 'low battery' warning during deployment as a faulty connection developed between the back-up battery and main battery.

13. Zooplankton sampling

Marc Lavaleye

A vertical plankton net (mesh size 200 µm) was used 3 times at one location above Rockall Mound (Sta. 10-12). The purpose was to sample the plankton in the upper water layer for stable isotope analyses. The procedure was as follows. The net was lowered to about 100m water depth with a speed of 10 m/min, and then hauled in again with the same speed to the surface. The catch was water drained and then frozen for later analyses. Surprisingly the three catches differed substantial in volume and content. A quick look under the microscope learned that the first catch consisted mainly of small copepods, the second was more varied with copepods, Tomopteris, Chaetognatha, jellies and large trochophora larvae. The third haul consisted mainly of copepods, Cladocera, and orange Globigerina.

Appendices

Appendix 1, CTD sample depths

Cruise	64PE420			pump depths				
Date	#####		pump 1					
Station	2		pump 2					
Cast	1		pump 3					
Depth	525 m							

Bottle	Depth (m)	Temperature	SPM	NUTS	SI	POM	DOC	DIC
1	525	8.7	A, B	X	X		X	X
2	525	8.7	incubation water			C, D		
3	525	8.7	incubation water					
4	525	8.7	incubation water					
5	525	8.7	incubation water					
6	525	8.7	incubation water					
7	525	8.7	incubation water					
8	525	8.7	incubation water					
9	525	8.7	incubation water					
10	525	8.7	incubation water					
11	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP
12	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP
13	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP
14	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP
15	525	8.7	incubation water					
16	525	8.7	incubation water					
17	152	10.1	E, F	X	X		X	X
18	152					G, H		
19	79	10.2	I, J	X	X		X	X
20	79					K, L		
21	10	10.2	M, N	X	X		X	X
22	10	10.2				O, P		
23								
24								

Cruise	64PE420			pump depths				
Date	#####		pump 1					
Station	19		pump 2					
Cast	1		pump 3					
Depth	540							

Bottle	Depth (m)	Temperature	SPM	NUTS	SI	POM	DOC	DIC
1	529			X (7)	X	X, 2	X	X
2	529							
3	510			X (8)	X		X	X
4	510							
5	480			X (9)	X		X	X
6	480							
7	430			X(10)	X		X	X
8	430							
9	230			X (11)	X		X	X
10	230							
11	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
12	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
13	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
14	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
15	30			X (12)	X	AA, AB	X	X
16	30							
17	30							
18	30							
19	30							
20	30							
21	30							
22	30							
23	30							
24	30							

Cruise	64PE420			pump depths				
Date	#####		pump 1					
Station	34		pump 2					
Cast	1		pump 3					
Depth	405 m							

Bottle	Depth (m)	Temperature	SPM	NUTS	SI	POM	DOC	DIC
1	390	9.09		X (17)	X	A, B		
2	390	9.09						
3	390	9.09		X (18)	X	C, D		
4	310	9.25						
5	310	9.25		X (19)	X	E, F		
6	310	9.25						
7	30	9.91						
8	30	9.91						
9	30	9.91						
10								
11	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
12	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
13	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
14	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
15								
16								
17								
18								
19								
20								
21								
22								
23								
24								

Cruise	64PE420			pump depths						
Date	#####			pump 1						
Station	61			pump 2						
Cast	1			pump 3						
Depth	815 m									
Bottle	Depth (m)	Temperature	SPM	NUTS	SI	POM	DOC	DIC		
1	815 (bot)									
2	815 (bot)									
3	815 (bot)									
4	815 (bot)									
5	815 (bot)									
6	815 (bot)									
7	815 (bot)									
8	815 (bot)									
9	815 (bot)									
10	815 (bot)			X	X	A, B	X	X		bact (7)
11	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP		
12	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP		
13	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP		
14	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP		
15	805 (+20)	10.26		X	X		X	X		bact (8)
16	805 (+20)	10.26								
17	775 (+50)			X	X		X	X		
18	775 (+50)									
19	725 (+100)			X	X		X	X		
20	725 (+100)									
21	625 (+200)			X	X		X	X		
22	625 (+200)									
23	25			X	X	C, D	X	X		bact (9)
24	25									

Cruise	64PE420				pump depths			
Date	#####				pump 1			
Station	77				pump 2			
Cast	1				pump 3			
Depth	995 m							

Bottle	Depth (m)	Temperature	SPM	NUTS	SI	POM	DOC	DIC
1	975	6.9				A, B		
2	975	6.9						
3	975	6.9						
4	700					C, D		
5	700							
6	700							
7	700							
8	700							
9	700							
10	700							
11	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
12	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
13	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
14	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP						
15	700							
16	700							
17	700							
18	700							
19	700							
20	700							
21	700							
22	700							
23	39					E, F		
24	39							

Cruise	64PE420				pump depths					
Date	#####				pump 1					
Station	86				pump 2					
Cast	1				pump 3					
Depth	545 m									
 Bottle	 Depth (m)	 Temperature	 SPM	 NUTS	 SI	 POM	 DOC	 DIC		
1	535									phyto
2	310									phyto
3	190									phyto
4	66									phyto
5	30									phyto
6	3									phyto
7										
8										
9										
10										
11	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	
12	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	
13	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	
14	IN SITU PUM	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	IN SITU PUMP	
15										
16										
17										
18										
19										
20										
21										
22										
23										
24										

Appendix 2, Activity list

Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude(deg. min.)	Longitude(deg. Min.)	Phase name	Device name	Action name
29/04/2017	19:07:21	N 55° 29.87088'	W 15° 47.08062'	STATION1	Mooring	Deployment
29/04/2017	19:34:35	N 55° 29.74638'	W 15° 48.00102'	STATION2	CTD with samples	Begin
29/04/2017	19:47:18	N 55° 29.7453'	W 15° 48.00102'		CTD with samples	Bottom
29/04/2017	20:46:11	N 55° 29.74572'	W 15° 47.98092'		CTD with samples	End
29/04/2017	21:38:48	N 55° 29.7426'	W 15° 48.0096'	STATION3	In situ pump	Begin
29/04/2017	22:59:12	N 55° 29.74572'	W 15° 48.03258'		In situ pump	Start pump
30/04/2017	06:58:50	N 55° 29.733'	W 15° 48.0006'		In situ pump	Stop pump
30/04/2017	08:46:26	N 55° 29.74392'	W 15° 48.01122'	STATION4	Boxcore	Bottom
30/04/2017	09:22:54	N 55° 29.75028'	W 15° 47.98422'	STATION5	Boxcore	Bottom
30/04/2017	10:24:17	N 55° 29.73912'	W 15° 48.02172'	STATION6	Boxcore	Bottom
30/04/2017	12:13:25	N 55° 29.72292'	W 15° 47.9946'	STATION7	Lander	Deployment
30/04/2017	13:48:34	N 55° 29.45202'	W 15° 47.62848'	STATION8	Boxcore	Bottom
30/04/2017	14:22:03	N 55° 29.44878'	W 15° 47.62788'	STATION9	Boxcore	Bottom
30/04/2017	15:49:04	N 55° 29.4387'	W 15° 47.64762'	STATION10	Vertical Net	Begin
30/04/2017	15:54:06	N 55° 29.4468'	W 15° 47.63958'		Vertical Net	Start Heave
30/04/2017	16:04:49	N 55° 29.4453'	W 15° 47.6325'		Vertical Net	End
30/04/2017	16:08:57	N 55° 29.45142'	W 15° 47.6253'	STATION11	Vertical Net	Begin
30/04/2017	16:13:39	N 55° 29.45298'	W 15° 47.63232'		Vertical Net	Start Heave
30/04/2017	16:24:09	N 55° 29.44728'	W 15° 47.61768'		Vertical Net	End
30/04/2017	16:28:56	N 55° 29.4453'	W 15° 47.6205'	STATION12	Vertical Net	Begin
30/04/2017	16:34:14	N 55° 29.43012'	W 15° 47.63208'		Vertical Net	Start Heave
30/04/2017	16:43:58	N 55° 29.45172'	W 15° 47.62878'		Vertical Net	End
30/04/2017	18:00:26	N 55° 29.67378'	W 15° 48.15258'	STATION13	In situ pump	Start pump
30/04/2017	22:06:03	N 55° 29.67108'	W 15° 48.18528'		In situ pump	Stop pump
30/04/2017	22:22:25	N 55° 29.67672'	W 15° 48.1764'		In situ pump	End
30/04/2017	23:09:20	N 55° 29.87898'	W 15° 52.32342'	STATION14	EK900 Track	Begin
01/05/2017	00:11:33	N 55° 29.4147'	W 15° 47.56092'		EK900 Track	Course Change
01/05/2017	07:48:08	N 55° 29.36532'	W 15° 47.46972'		EK900 Track	End
01/05/2017	08:19:08	N 55° 29.37378'	W 15° 47.4633'	STATION15	ROV	Begin
01/05/2017	08:57:31	N 55° 29.37822'	W 15° 47.49072'		ROV	End
01/05/2017	09:31:42	N 55° 29.3592'	W 15° 47.45532'	STATION16	ROV	Begin
01/05/2017	09:53:06	N 55° 29.39142'	W 15° 47.48022'		ROV	End
01/05/2017	11:56:24	N 55° 29.74932'	W 15° 47.98752'	STATION17	In situ pump	Start pump
01/05/2017	16:08:39	N 55° 29.75262'	W 15° 47.96088'		In situ pump	Stop pump
01/05/2017	17:15:56	N 55° 29.71152'	W 15° 47.97582'	STATION18	Lander	Recovery
01/05/2017	19:20:07	N 55° 29.7582'	W 15° 48.01212'	STATION19	CTD with samples	Begin
01/05/2017	19:32:34	N 55° 29.75322'	W 15° 47.9934'		CTD with samples	Bottom
01/05/2017	19:56:44	N 55° 29.74998'	W 15° 47.99928'		CTD with samples	End
01/05/2017	20:28:45	N 55° 29.37132'	W 15° 47.47518'	STATION20	EK900 Track	Begin

Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude(deg. min.)	Longitude(deg. Min.)	Phase name	Device name	Action name
02/05/2017	05:59:46	N 55° 29.3682'	W 15° 47.44608'		EK900 Track	End
02/05/2017	06:03:42	N 55° 29.51502'	W 15° 47.66088'	TRANSIT1		
02/05/2017	09:01:56	N 55° 38.44818'	W 15° 55.839'	STATION21	Mooring	Deployment
02/05/2017	10:24:49	N 55° 38.12922'	W 15° 55.71642'	STATION22	Boxcore	Bottom
02/05/2017	11:21:48	N 55° 38.4006'	W 15° 55.26738'	STATION23	Boxcore	Bottom
02/05/2017	12:06:16	N 55° 38.21868'	W 15° 55.40322'	STATION24	Boxcore	Bottom
02/05/2017	13:36:54	N 55° 38.172'	W 15° 56.03238'	STATION25	Boxcore	Bottom
02/05/2017	14:27:03	N 55° 38.40282'	W 15° 56.21742'	STATION26	Lander	Deployment
02/05/2017	15:36:09	N 55° 38.39088'	W 15° 56.21838'	STATION27	ROV	Begin
02/05/2017	15:45:36	N 55° 38.37342'	W 15° 56.1933'		ROV	End
02/05/2017	15:51:45	N 55° 38.37738'	W 15° 56.2059'	STATION28	ROV	Begin
02/05/2017	16:12:12	N 55° 38.3778'	W 15° 56.25372'		ROV	End
03/05/2017	01:59:37	N 55° 38.39982'	W 15° 56.2599'	STATION29	In situ pump	Start pump
03/05/2017	06:00:03	N 55° 38.39892'	W 15° 56.24328'		In situ pump	Stop pump
03/05/2017	08:40:53	N 55° 38.418'	W 15° 56.27112'	STATION30	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	09:07:20	N 55° 38.448'	W 15° 56.09712'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	09:31:55	N 55° 40.43148'	W 15° 56.83638'	STATION31	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	09:40:06	N 55° 40.43652'	W 15° 56.83938'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	09:53:49	N 55° 40.39428'	W 15° 56.80818'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	10:17:16	N 55° 42.34188'	W 15° 57.66108'	STATION32	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	10:26:41	N 55° 42.33558'	W 15° 57.69288'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	10:36:02	N 55° 42.33678'	W 15° 57.6585'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	10:59:37	N 55° 44.2845'	W 15° 58.42932'	STATION33	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	11:07:58	N 55° 44.28648'	W 15° 58.4454'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	11:18:12	N 55° 44.2782'	W 15° 58.44762'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	11:45:45	N 55° 46.22232'	W 15° 59.23482'	STATION34	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2017	11:53:31	N 55° 46.2129'	W 15° 59.2329'		CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2017	12:09:25	N 55° 46.1976'	W 15° 59.1993'		CTD with samples	End
03/05/2017	13:28:58	N 55° 56.1255'	W 16° 2.9235'	STATION35	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	13:37:19	N 55° 56.12592'	W 16° 2.8872'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	13:44:38	N 55° 56.11692'	W 16° 2.8989'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	16:08:28	N 55° 38.44038'	W 15° 56.17248'	STATION36	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2017	16:21:34	N 55° 38.4282'	W 15° 56.20752'		CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2017	16:41:32	N 55° 38.42808'	W 15° 56.1969'		CTD with samples	End
03/05/2017	17:12:01	N 55° 38.48268'	W 15° 56.02728'	STATION37	Lander	Recovery
03/05/2017	18:40:58	N 55° 38.41782'	W 15° 56.21058'	STATION38	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	18:52:32	N 55° 38.41542'	W 15° 56.20908'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	19:01:52	N 55° 38.4087'	W 15° 56.20548'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	19:04:11	N 55° 38.41152'	W 15° 56.18808'	STATION39	CTD	Begin

Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude(deg. min.)	Longitude(deg. Min.)	Phase name	Device name	Action name
03/05/2017	19:13:17	N 55° 38.4147'	W 15° 56.20218'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	19:22:36	N 55° 38.42238'	W 15° 56.18712'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	19:24:00	N 55° 38.42382'	W 15° 56.19'	STATION40	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	19:33:23	N 55° 38.4129'	W 15° 56.17728'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	19:42:48	N 55° 38.4276'	W 15° 56.187'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	19:44:07	N 55° 38.42502'	W 15° 56.1969'	STATION41	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	19:53:40	N 55° 38.42322'	W 15° 56.19288'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	20:02:57	N 55° 38.42232'	W 15° 56.20608'		CTD	End
03/05/2017	20:04:40	N 55° 38.4216'	W 15° 56.19222'	STATION42	CTD	Begin
03/05/2017	20:14:18	N 55° 38.4432'	W 15° 56.20752'		CTD	Bottom
03/05/2017	20:23:54	N 55° 38.42862'	W 15° 56.20812'		CTD	End
04/05/2017	02:44:48	N 55° 38.42412'	W 15° 56.14488'	STATION43	In situ pump	Start pump
04/05/2017	06:45:01	N 55° 38.4273'	W 15° 56.19522'		In situ pump	Stop pump
04/05/2017	07:17:20	N 55° 38.4534'	W 15° 56.2005'	TRANSIT2		
04/05/2017	08:49:47	N 55° 27.0477'	W 15° 52.1175'	STATION44	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2017	09:05:34	N 55° 27.03948'	W 15° 52.13892'		CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2017	09:23:12	N 55° 27.0384'	W 15° 52.11828'		CTD with samples	End
04/05/2017	10:31:38	N 55° 27.03708'	W 15° 52.13058'	STATION45	Boxcore	Bottom
04/05/2017	11:19:04	N 55° 27.03972'	W 15° 52.134'	STATION46	Boxcore	Bottom
04/05/2017	11:56:52	N 55° 27.08862'	W 15° 51.9582'	TRANSIT3		
04/05/2017	13:26:39	N 55° 29.19408'	W 15° 48.19278'	STATION47	Boxcore	Bottom
04/05/2017	14:15:31	N 55° 29.20008'	W 15° 48.1857'	STATION48	Boxcore	Bottom
04/05/2017	15:30:12	N 55° 29.20332'	W 15° 48.20358'	STATION49	Lander	Deployment
04/05/2017	15:54:26	N 55° 29.2053'	W 15° 48.19098'	STATION50	ROV	Begin
04/05/2017	16:12:53	N 55° 29.20452'	W 15° 48.20082'		ROV	Bottom
04/05/2017	17:12:51	N 55° 29.19588'	W 15° 48.20118'		ROV	Start Heave
04/05/2017	17:43:36	N 55° 29.2071'	W 15° 48.19908'		ROV	End
05/05/2017	03:29:28	N 55° 28.9509'	W 15° 47.84622'	STATION51	In situ pump	Start pump
05/05/2017	07:30:04	N 55° 28.94262'	W 15° 47.8482'		In situ pump	Stop pump
05/05/2017	08:46:37	N 55° 29.27178'	W 15° 48.44802'	STATION52	Boxcore	Bottom
05/05/2017	11:12:52	N 55° 29.24952'	W 15° 48.44178'	STATION53	Boxcore	Bottom
05/05/2017	13:21:55	N 55° 29.26068'	W 15° 48.4554'	STATION54	Boxcore	Bottom
05/05/2017	14:49:15	N 55° 26.1492'	W 15° 51.93138'	STATION55	CTD	Begin
05/05/2017	15:17:04	N 55° 26.1384'	W 15° 51.89022'		CTD	Bottom
05/05/2017	15:37:51	N 55° 26.13528'	W 15° 51.87708'		CTD	End
05/05/2017	16:13:15	N 55° 29.06028'	W 15° 53.03418'	STATION56	CTD	Begin
05/05/2017	16:32:55	N 55° 29.0604'	W 15° 53.0124'		CTD	Bottom
05/05/2017	16:50:38	N 55° 29.05632'	W 15° 53.0394'		CTD	End
05/05/2017	17:28:21	N 55° 32.03172'	W 15° 54.12642'	STATION57	CTD	Begin

Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude(deg. min.)	Longitude(deg. Min.)	Phase name	Device name	Action name
05/05/2017	17:41:46	N 55° 32.01702'	W 15° 54.11448'		CTD	Bottom
05/05/2017	18:09:32	N 55° 32.01558'	W 15° 54.11268'		CTD	End
05/05/2017	19:00:51	N 55° 34.9554'	W 15° 55.10838'	STATION58	CTD	Begin
05/05/2017	19:13:04	N 55° 34.95672'	W 15° 55.09692'		CTD	Bottom
05/05/2017	19:23:41	N 55° 34.9353'	W 15° 55.08852'		CTD	End
05/05/2017	20:06:04	N 55° 37.91232'	W 15° 55.9656'	STATION59	CTD	Begin
05/05/2017	20:14:48	N 55° 37.9212'	W 15° 55.95732'		CTD	Bottom
05/05/2017	20:23:36	N 55° 37.9035'	W 15° 55.98342'		CTD	End
05/05/2017	20:57:08	N 55° 40.82922'	W 15° 56.9637'	STATION60	CTD	Begin
05/05/2017	21:05:04	N 55° 40.8381'	W 15° 56.9613'		CTD	Bottom
05/05/2017	21:13:19	N 55° 40.84458'	W 15° 56.99142'		CTD	End
05/05/2017	21:18:44	N 55° 40.8381'	W 15° 57.06258'	TRANSIT4		
06/05/2017	08:12:49	N 55° 29.01438'	W 15° 48.55158'	STATION61	CTD with samples	Begin
06/05/2017	08:23:40	N 55° 29.0187'	W 15° 48.5514'		CTD with samples	Bottom
06/05/2017	08:49:07	N 55° 29.0142'	W 15° 48.53292'		CTD with samples	End
06/05/2017	09:42:01	N 55° 29.1609'	W 15° 48.46248'	STATION62	Lander	Recovery
06/05/2017	10:37:52	N 55° 29.45622'	W 15° 47.65338'	STATION63	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	11:31:12	N 55° 29.451'	W 15° 47.63382'	STATION64	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	13:40:23	N 55° 29.75028'	W 15° 47.98242'	STATION65	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	14:46:32	N 55° 27.0468'	W 15° 52.13088'	STATION66	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	15:30:12	N 55° 27.0342'	W 15° 52.14612'	STATION67	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	16:48:32	N 55° 27.0015'	W 15° 52.10862'	STATION68	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	17:23:03	N 55° 26.99868'	W 15° 52.10112'	STATION69	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	18:51:57	N 55° 26.89782'	W 15° 52.40952'	STATION70	Boxcore	Bottom
06/05/2017	19:51:18	N 55° 26.988'	W 15° 52.1019'	STATION71	CTD	Begin
06/05/2017	20:07:10	N 55° 27.00108'	W 15° 52.1076'		CTD	Bottom
06/05/2017	20:19:51	N 55° 27.00222'	W 15° 52.0971'		CTD	End
07/05/2017	02:59:14	N 55° 26.98332'	W 15° 52.06488'	STATION72	In situ pump	Start pump
07/05/2017	07:45:10	N 55° 26.99892'	W 15° 52.10898'		In situ pump	Stop pump
07/05/2017	09:06:49	N 55° 26.92092'	W 15° 52.39998'	STATION73	Boxcore	Bottom
07/05/2017	10:26:00	N 55° 26.41818'	W 15° 51.82422'	STATION74	ROV	Bottom
07/05/2017	12:39:50	N 55° 27.11088'	W 15° 52.22262'		ROV	Start Heave
07/05/2017	13:58:19	N 55° 27.16398'	W 15° 52.31268'	STATION75	Lander	Deployment
07/05/2017	15:48:24	N 55° 25.02132'	W 15° 55.4475'	STATION76	ROV	Bottom
07/05/2017	17:18:05	N 55° 25.56222'	W 15° 55.6578'		ROV	Start Heave
07/05/2017	18:50:49	N 55° 26.69892'	W 15° 52.00302'	STATION77	CTD	Begin
07/05/2017	19:11:35	N 55° 26.6961'	W 15° 52.00008'		CTD	Bottom
07/05/2017	19:37:48	N 55° 26.69742'	W 15° 51.9999'		CTD	End
07/05/2017	20:13:34	N 55° 26.99382'	W 15° 52.1172'	STATION78	CTD	Begin

Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude(deg. min.)	Longitude(deg. Min.)	Phase name	Device name	Action name
07/05/2017	20:28:30	N 55° 27.00852'	W 15° 52.1103'		CTD	Bottom
07/05/2017	20:42:59	N 55° 26.99952'	W 15° 52.0779'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	02:58:10	N 55° 27.00012'	W 15° 52.06308'	STATION79	In situ pump	Start pump
08/05/2017	07:00:03	N 55° 26.99298'	W 15° 52.0647'		In situ pump	Stop pump
08/05/2017	08:21:09	N 55° 26.9982'	W 15° 52.09542'	STATION80	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	08:35:20	N 55° 27.0075'	W 15° 52.11582'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	08:54:01	N 55° 27.00252'	W 15° 52.08282'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	09:21:48	N 55° 28.48818'	W 15° 52.63458'	STATION81	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	09:42:32	N 55° 28.47918'	W 15° 52.6326'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	09:54:27	N 55° 28.4793'	W 15° 52.6329'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	10:13:43	N 55° 29.91282'	W 15° 53.1711'	STATION82	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	10:30:23	N 55° 29.92068'	W 15° 53.13858'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	10:46:43	N 55° 29.9223'	W 15° 53.1567'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	11:07:14	N 55° 31.3614'	W 15° 53.70882'	STATION83	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	11:22:20	N 55° 31.35972'	W 15° 53.67972'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	11:37:08	N 55° 31.3578'	W 15° 53.6868'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	11:57:59	N 55° 32.8656'	W 15° 54.26718'	STATION84	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	12:13:05	N 55° 32.8518'	W 15° 54.23838'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	12:24:42	N 55° 32.84952'	W 15° 54.22998'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	12:57:55	N 55° 34.33602'	W 15° 54.7968'	STATION85	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	13:09:45	N 55° 34.34532'	W 15° 54.7743'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	13:20:49	N 55° 34.3542'	W 15° 54.76572'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	13:39:57	N 55° 35.7555'	W 15° 55.34412'	STATION86	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	13:52:30	N 55° 35.76438'	W 15° 55.2804'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	14:12:03	N 55° 35.77698'	W 15° 55.2678'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	14:48:03	N 55° 37.30458'	W 15° 55.89738'	STATION87	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	15:00:21	N 55° 37.28202'	W 15° 55.8648'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	15:10:40	N 55° 37.27782'	W 15° 55.83702'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	15:31:33	N 55° 38.70168'	W 15° 56.4225'	STATION88	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	15:45:32	N 55° 38.71608'	W 15° 56.33952'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	15:51:39	N 55° 38.7069'	W 15° 56.34108'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	16:15:03	N 55° 40.1688'	W 15° 56.91138'	STATION89	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	16:24:09	N 55° 40.17312'	W 15° 56.90322'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	16:34:09	N 55° 40.16862'	W 15° 56.913'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	16:57:36	N 55° 41.6439'	W 15° 57.43548'	STATION90	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	17:05:31	N 55° 41.63652'	W 15° 57.44952'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	17:13:59	N 55° 41.6337'	W 15° 57.43578'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	17:35:23	N 55° 43.11138'	W 15° 57.97278'	STATION91	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	17:43:30	N 55° 43.11138'	W 15° 57.948'		CTD	Bottom

Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude(deg. min.)	Longitude(deg. Min.)	Phase name	Device name	Action name
08/05/2017	17:51:36	N 55° 43.1118'	W 15° 57.95502'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	18:30:04	N 55° 44.58618'	W 15° 58.47078'	STATION92	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	18:39:59	N 55° 44.58432'	W 15° 58.4583'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	18:48:13	N 55° 44.5911'	W 15° 58.45662'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	19:10:35	N 55° 46.065'	W 15° 58.9629'	STATION93	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	19:19:43	N 55° 46.0653'	W 15° 58.962'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	19:27:53	N 55° 46.0653'	W 15° 58.95372'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	19:53:42	N 55° 47.5641'	W 15° 59.46408'	STATION94	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	19:57:08	N 55° 47.56278'	W 15° 59.46402'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	20:04:44	N 55° 47.55678'	W 15° 59.46768'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	20:25:27	N 55° 49.07292'	W 15° 59.97258'	STATION95	CTD	Begin
08/05/2017	20:32:53	N 55° 49.0758'	W 15° 59.97618'		CTD	Bottom
08/05/2017	20:40:14	N 55° 49.0677'	W 15° 59.973'		CTD	End
08/05/2017	20:50:30	N 55° 48.99948'	W 16° 0.0423'	TRANSIT5		
09/05/2017	08:06:30	N 55° 27.05202'	W 15° 52.17432'	STATION96	CTD with samples	Begin
09/05/2017	08:21:41	N 55° 27.06468'	W 15° 52.17618'		CTD with samples	Bottom
09/05/2017	08:49:41	N 55° 27.0597'	W 15° 52.1589'		CTD with samples	End
09/05/2017	09:26:06	N 55° 27.24732'	W 15° 52.7472'	STATION97	Lander	Recovery
09/05/2017	11:07:21	N 55° 27.048'	W 15° 51.96798'	STATION98	Mooring	Deployment
09/05/2017	13:29:29	N 55° 29.83188'	W 15° 47.03598'	STATION99	Mooring	Recovery
09/05/2017	14:59:53	N 55° 26.739'	W 15° 51.98028'	STATION100	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	15:17:49	N 55° 26.709'	W 15° 51.9768'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	15:37:56	N 55° 26.70522'	W 15° 51.97932'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	15:56:34	N 55° 26.71092'	W 15° 51.96192'	STATION101	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	16:15:48	N 55° 26.69412'	W 15° 51.98922'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	16:33:09	N 55° 26.69418'	W 15° 52.01448'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	16:34:59	N 55° 26.6934'	W 15° 52.0083'	STATION102	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	16:51:42	N 55° 26.70342'	W 15° 51.9984'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	17:08:38	N 55° 26.69172'	W 15° 52.01352'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	17:09:40	N 55° 26.69142'	W 15° 52.0158'	STATION103	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	17:27:15	N 55° 26.69382'	W 15° 52.00512'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	17:46:09	N 55° 26.68938'	W 15° 52.02162'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	17:47:16	N 55° 26.69178'	W 15° 52.0203'	STATION104	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	18:05:27	N 55° 26.69502'	W 15° 52.00218'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	18:22:55	N 55° 26.694'	W 15° 51.98958'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	18:23:55	N 55° 26.6928'	W 15° 51.9936'	STATION105	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	18:41:59	N 55° 26.6937'	W 15° 52.02192'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	18:59:45	N 55° 26.70138'	W 15° 51.99528'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	19:00:17	N 55° 26.70072'	W 15° 51.99558'	STATION106	CTD	Begin

Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude(deg. min.)	Longitude(deg. Min.)	Phase name	Device name	Action name
09/05/2017	19:20:17	N 55° 26.6979'	W 15° 52.01568'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	19:38:46	N 55° 26.70192'	W 15° 52.0068'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	19:39:50	N 55° 26.70198'	W 15° 52.00692'	STATION107	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	19:59:36	N 55° 26.7012'	W 15° 51.9933'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	20:18:16	N 55° 26.69952'	W 15° 51.99228'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	20:19:04	N 55° 26.6997'	W 15° 51.99048'	STATION108	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	20:38:35	N 55° 26.69298'	W 15° 51.9885'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	20:57:46	N 55° 26.6844'	W 15° 51.99378'	STATION109	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	21:15:56	N 55° 26.68728'	W 15° 51.9879'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	21:33:52	N 55° 26.6937'	W 15° 51.99072'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	21:35:01	N 55° 26.6982'	W 15° 51.98682'	STATION110	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	21:53:01	N 55° 26.70678'	W 15° 51.98142'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	22:11:36	N 55° 26.7045'	W 15° 51.99798'		CTD	End
09/05/2017	22:12:29	N 55° 26.7051'	W 15° 52.00098'	STATION111	CTD	Begin
09/05/2017	22:32:14	N 55° 26.7078'	W 15° 52.00002'		CTD	Bottom
09/05/2017	22:51:20	N 55° 26.70252'	W 15° 52.0047'		CTD	End
10/05/2017	03:44:03	N 55° 26.72862'	W 15° 51.98472'	STATION112	In situ pump	Start pump
10/05/2017	07:45:05	N 55° 26.703'	W 15° 52.02612'		In situ pump	Stop pump
10/05/2017	08:48:29	N 55° 26.70102'	W 15° 52.0416'	STATION113	CTD	Begin
10/05/2017	09:05:42	N 55° 26.68668'	W 15° 52.0116'		CTD	Bottom
10/05/2017	09:23:23	N 55° 26.69982'	W 15° 52.01832'		CTD	End
10/05/2017	09:24:51	N 55° 26.70042'	W 15° 52.0155'	STATION114	CTD	Begin
10/05/2017	09:41:18	N 55° 26.69592'	W 15° 52.01712'		CTD	Bottom
10/05/2017	09:58:54	N 55° 26.69772'	W 15° 52.02558'		CTD	End
10/05/2017	09:59:55	N 55° 26.69808'	W 15° 52.02708'	STATION115	CTD	Begin
10/05/2017	10:17:47	N 55° 26.6931'	W 15° 52.03248'		CTD	Bottom
10/05/2017	10:35:32	N 55° 26.69748'	W 15° 52.03062'		CTD	End

Appendix 3, Filters

Filter nr	Station	Depth (m)	Gear type	L filtered	
17B01	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	Lander at summit Haas mound
17B02	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B03	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B04	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B05	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B06	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B07	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B09	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B10	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B11	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B12	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B13	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B14	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B15	64PE420-18	533	McLane	10	
17B16	64PE420-02	525	CTD	10	Calibration CTD
17B17	64PE420-02	152	CTD	10	
17B18	64PE420-02	79	CTD	10	
17B19	64PE420-02	10	CTD	10	
17B20	64PE420-19	529	CTD	10	CTD at summit Haas mound, at lander station
17B21	64PE420-19	30	CTD	10	
17B22	Blanco				
17B24	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	Lander at Bank
17B25	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B26	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B27	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B28	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B29	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B30	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B31	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B32	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B33	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B34	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B35	64PE420-37	482	McLane	10	
17B36	64PE420-34	390	CTD	10	CTD at bank
17B37	64PE420-34	310	CTD	10	
17B38	64PE420-34	30	CTD	5	
17B39	64PE420-36	467	CTD	10	CTD at bank, lander station
17B40	64PE420-36	25	CTD	10	
17B41	Blanco				
17B42	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	Lander south of Haas mound
17B43	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B44	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B45	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B46	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B47	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B48	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B49	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B50	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	

47 mm Filters

Filter nr	Station	Depth (m)	Gear type	L filtered	
17B51	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B52	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B53	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B54	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B55	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B56	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B57	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B58	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B59	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B60	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	
17B61	64PE420-62	737	McLane	10	In surface water during recovery
17B62	64PE420-62	737	McLane		no sample
17B63	64PE420-62	737	McLane		no sample
17B64	64PE420-62	737	McLane		no sample
17B65	64PE420-62	737	McLane		no sample
17B66	64PE420-61	825	CTD	10	CTD South of Haas mound
17B67	64PE420-61	25	CTD	5	
17B68	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	Lander at Oreo mound
17B69	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B70	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B71	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B72	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B73	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B74	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B75	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B76	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B77	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B78	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B79	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B80	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B81	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B82	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B83	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B84	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B85	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B86	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B87	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B88	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B89	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B90	64PE420-97	745	McLane	10	
17B91	64PE420-77	975	CTD	10	
17B92	64PE420-77	700	CTD	10	
17B93	64PE420-77	39	CTD	5	
17B94	Blanco				
17B95	64PE420-96	780	CTD	10	
17B96	64PE420-96	25	CTD	5	

47 mm Filters

Filter nr	Station	Depth (m)	Gear type	L filtered
317	64PE420-18	533	Profile pump	5
318	64PE420-18	533	Profile pump	5
319	64PE420-18	533	Profile pump	5
320	64PE420-18	533	Profile pump	5
322	64PE420-18	533	Profile pump	4.8
321	64PE420-18	533	Profile pump	4.8
322	Blanco			
323	64PE420-37	482	Profile pump	5
324	64PE420-37	482	Profile pump	5
325	64PE420-37	482	Profile pump	5
326	64PE420-37	482	Profile pump	4.8
327	64PE420-37	482	Profile pump	3.5
328	64PE420-37	482	Profile pump	3.3
329	Blanco			
330	64PE420-62	737	Profile pump	5
331	64PE420-62	737	Profile pump	3.9
332	64PE420-62	737	Profile pump	5
333	64PE420-62	737	Profile pump	4.45
334	64PE420-62	737	Profile pump	4
335	64PE420-62	737	Profile pump	4.3
336	64PE420-97	745	Profile pump	5
337	64PE420-97	745	Profile pump	4.15
338	64PE420-97	745	Profile pump	5
339	64PE420-97	745	Profile pump	5
360	64PE420-97	745	Profile pump	5
361	64PE420-97	745	Profile pump	5

25 mm Filters

Surviving in a Deep-Sea Desert – Uncovering the Functioning of Cold-Water Coral Reefs in the Deep Ocean

26-4-2017

Dick van Oevelen and Gert-Jan Reichart

The deep seafloor harbours one of the most biodiverse ecosystems on our planet: cold-water coral reefs. Like their tropical counterparts, cold-water corals (CWCs) form structurally complex habitats that support a diverse and productive reef community. It is still paradoxical how such a rich ecosystem can thrive in the deep sea, an environment that is typically considered to be food limited.

A group of scientists, funded by NWO (VIDI program) and the EU (www.eu-atlas.org), collectively target this paradox during the present cruise with the Dutch research vessel *Pelagia*. They will visit Rockall Bank (West of Ireland) which has amongst the highest abundance of cold-water coral reefs in the world.

During this research expedition, they will deploy instruments in the water column above the reef for one year to study the processes that govern the delivery of organic matter towards the deep reefs. In addition, they will use targeted sampling of reef organisms by the remotely operated vehicle *Genesis* (www.vliz.be/nl/rov-genesis) to determine how much and which food sources these organisms are utilizing.

Photo: The research vessel Pelagia is being prepared for departure in NIOZ harbour of Texel.

May 3rd, blog by Wim Versteeg

During this expedition, the Remote Operating Vehicle (ROV) "Genesis" from the VLIZ (a 1500m depth-rated ROV-Cherokee manufactured by Sub-Atlantic) is used for video-surveying and sampling of the organisms living at the cold-water coral reef bed. Last year this ROV was renewed and upgraded with single-mode glass-fiber transmission, HD-, Low Light- and Stills- cameras and High-Power and Wide-Angle LED-lights (see included photos). A GAPS-USBL-system is used for the real-time positioning of the RV-Pelagia, ROV, TMS and if needed landers during a ROV-dive. All these complex techniques have to function together to accurately observe and sample from a seafloor that is covered with corals.

We had some misfortune during the first two dives. First there was a 3000V short-cut in the system and during the second dive the LED-lights stopped working. Both problems were repaired by the joint VLIZ-NIOZ team and at this moment we are waiting for a window in the weather conditions to start the next dive. The team operating this vehicle consists of Ruud Groenewegen (Royal NIOZ), Michiel T'Jampens and Wim Versteeg (both VLIZ).

Detecting the direction of food transport to deep-sea coral mounds

May 6th, blog by Gerard Duineveld

During the ATLAS cruise two mooring lines will be deployed each of which holds a profiling current meter (ADCP), sediment trap, and sensors to measure chlorophyll and particle density. In the meantime, one mooring line has been put on the seafloor at the shallow part of Rockall Bank at 450 m water depth. The spot is outside the area where mounds are found overgrown with cold water corals (Logachev Mounds). The other mooring line is scheduled to be deployed in a few days at a much deeper site on top of a coral mound densely populated by the cold water coral *Lophelia pertusa*.

Earlier measurements by NIOZ at the Logachev Mounds showed the coral mounds to be hotspots of carbon consumption and storage. This raised questions about where the food for the corals on the mounds is coming from: from the upper water column over the mounds in the form of vertically sinking particles, or from algae produced at the shallow parts of Rockall Bank and carried to the

mounds by tidal currents. With the two moorings we intend to detect when and from which direction the food is transported towards the coral mounds.

Quantifying the metabolism of complex cold water coral communities in situ

May 7th, blog by Lorenzo Rovelli

During the ATLAS cruise an Aquatic Eddy Co-variance (AEC) system from the University of Southern Denmark will be used to quantify the metabolism of complex CWC communities in situ. The AEC system consists of an acoustic velocimeter (ADV), fast oxygen microsensors modules, and will be deployed on the NIOZ ALBEX lander. The main advantage of the AEC approach is that it provides an assessment of whole community metabolism over large areas of the mounds (up to 80 m²) without altering the local hydrodynamics and food supply. The aim is to characterize and compare the metabolism of the different communities located on the summit and flanks of the targeted mounds in the study area.

The AEC system was successfully deployed on coral rubble at the summit of Haas mound, but suffered some damage during the ALBEX lander retrieval under rough sea. Thanks to the help of the NIOZ technical staff, the system has been restored and the original safety cage rebuilt to better protect the instrument. The system was positively redeployed during the latest ALBEX lander deployment on the Haas mound flank and will be further deployed at the summit of Oreo mound.

Communicating with a bottom lander at the seafloor

May 9th, blog by Furu Mienis

To measure the variability in environmental conditions near the seabed we deployed an ALBEX bottom lander at several mounds amidst the corals. The NIOZ designed ALBEX lander (similar to a Mars lander) is a freefalling lander that can be deployed at the seabed for several days up to a year. It consists of an aluminium tripod frame on which different instruments can be mounted. In addition it contains two acoustic releases, 13 flotation spheres and a large bottom weight, which holds the lander at the seafloor. Since sound travels easily through water we recover the lander via an acoustic signal. By sending a sound with a specific frequency the release mechanism will open and due to the flotation spheres the lander will slowly rise up to the seafloor after which we can recover it.

During the current cruise the lander is equipped with the AEC system (see previous blog), a current meter to measure current direction and speed and an oxygen sensor. In addition we have mounted a particle pump to sample particles through time (one sample every 2 hours) to study changes in the type and amount of particles in the vicinity of the reef. These filtered samples will be analysed at NIOZ to determine if these particles can serve as food source for the corals and associated reef fauna. During this cruise we have also for the first time used a newly designed profile pump. This pump takes 6 samples from 20 cm up to 3 m above the seafloor in one go, allowing us to take samples in a gradient above the seafloor. We use this pumped system to measure if the coral framework changes the conditions in the layer close to the bottom. Samples will show us if there is a reef effect that causes depletion or enrichment of dissolved as well as particulate matter. So far we have carried out 3 successful deployments and tomorrow we will recover the lander for the last time during this cruise.

Boxcore incubations

Blog by Evert de Froe, May 10th 2017

The coral mounds at Rockall bank are not only densely covered by cold-water corals, but also by Crinoidea, Stylasteridea and various sponges (Fig. 1). A lot of food, a scarce commodity in the deep sea, is necessary to sustain this abundant life. One method to quantify how much food is actually utilised, is by measuring the metabolic activity of the reef. On this expedition we use various methods, amongst others whole boxcore incubations. The Haja boxcorer, developed by NIOZ, is used to sample 0.25 m² of the coral reef and lift it on board of RV Pelagia. The box core is subsequently closed airtight and incubated in cooling containers for one or two days (Fig. 2). This method gives a robust measure of the metabolic activity of the reef framework and allows us to compare oxygen consumption between areas, and methods.

Thanks to the skilful crew of the RV Pelagia, we managed to get seven successful box cores on deck. At this moment, the last incubation is running and the first results look promising.

Fig.1: The Oreomound at Rockall bank is densely populated with corals, Crinoids and sponges. The mound is named after the fish that is visible in this picture.

Pumping for sPOM

by Sabena Blackbird

During the ATLAS cruise McLane Large Volume Water Transfer System Sampler (WTS-LV) in-situ pumps were deployed at stations at Haas Mound, Bank and Oreo Mound at three depths in the water column – 20mab, 120mab and surface.

The in-situ pumps filtered up to 1400 L of water through an acid-washed 50 µm nylon mesh before a pre-ashed glass fibre filter with a nominal pore-size of 0.7 µm collecting the suspended particulate organic matter (sPOM). Back in the labs at the University of Liverpool we will further investigate these two size fractions of the sPOM using a variety of instrumental techniques to gain a greater understanding of the food resources available to the CWCs. This may include relatively unaltered fresh phytoplankton sPOM as well as reworked material forced into the water column through tidal dynamics.

Particulate organic carbon and particulate nitrogen concentrations and molar C/N ratios will be determined via Elemental Analysis (EA). The organic chemical composition (quality) will be assessed by quantitative determination of lipid biological markers such as polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), alcohols, sterols etc. using Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS). Further compound specific isotope analysis of the lipids will involve Isotope Ratio – Mass Spectrometry (IR-MS)

Huge thanks to the 'Pump Team Crew' Cor, Ewout, Martin and Wim for their skill in pump deployment and recovery even during some choppy sea conditions!

END